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Confinement of Lauric Acid into the Lumen of Halloysite Nanotubes

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Abstract

Molecules confined within nanometer-scale environments frequently exhibit a distinct physical response in contrast to those found in bulk conditions. In this study, intercalates of lauric acid (LA) were synthesized within halloysite nanotubes (HNT), successfully trapping 12 wt% of LA within the internal HNT tube, as demonstrated by transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and wide-angle and small-angle X-ray scattering (WAXS/SAXS) techniques. Furthermore, we noted that the confinement of LA within the HNT lumen resulted in a significant reduction in LA crystallinity, consistent with the impact of geometric constraints on crystallization behavior. The presence of a significant amorphous phase in the intercalates proved beneficial for the gradual release of LA into water, as evidenced by pH changes. Remarkably, the necessity of employing a vacuum

method and extended contact time (72 h) for the physical entrapment of LA in ethanol within the HNT lumen was found to be unnecessary, as similar physical characteristics were observed in an intercalate generated without vacuum and with very short contact time (< 1 h). Finally, we observed that the source of HNT is crucial in determining the final properties of the confined material.

Introduction

Halloysite nanotube (HNT) is physically and chemically analogous to kaolinite ($\text{Al}_2\text{SiO}_5(\text{OH})_4 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$). However, a monolayer of H_2O molecules is intercalated into halloysite giving a basal spacing near 10 \AA ($n=2$).^[1, 2] As the interlayer of water is held weakly, under ambient circumstances of temperature or humidity, HNT- 10\AA can readily and irreversibly dehydrate to give the corresponding halloysite- 7 \AA ($n = 0$).^[1, 2] Hence it is complicated to handle without modifying its hydration status. Several nano and micro containers have been used by researchers in recent years as reservoirs for inhibitors and self-healing agents such as montmorillonite nanoparticles, nano- TiO_2 , zirconia nanoparticles, cellulose microfibrils, urea-formaldehyde microcapsules (UFMCS), and melamine urea-formaldehyde microcapsules (MUFMCS).^[3-7] Among the nanocontainers, clays with a hollow structure such as halloysite nanotubes act as excellent nanocontainer for loading active agents due to their high surface area, good dispersion, ability to load several active agents simultaneously, high loading rate, high capacity, high porosity and non-toxicity.^[8] Generally, HNT length ranges between a few microns to $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ with an external diameter and internal diameter of 30 to 190 nm and 10 to 100 nm, respectively.^[9] The outer surface contains negatively charged tetrahedral silicate SiO_2 layers whereas the inner lumen consists of positively charged gibbsite octahedral layers

of Al_2O_3 .^[10] The specific surface area and cation exchange capability of this tubular structure range from 22.1 to 81.6 m^2/g and 0.1 to 0.7 meq/kg, respectively.^[11] HNT has 10.7 to 39% of lumen space and shows relatively lower density of 2.14 to 2.59 g/cm^3 .^[11] The huge lumen space provides an advantage for the uptake of active substances.

A wide variety of substances can be loaded into HNT and these substances can interact with HNT by adsorption, intercalation, and tubular entrapment.^[2, 10] In adsorption process, the adsorbate solute and HNT (solute sorbate) are usually mixed by stirring for almost 24 h to ensure that thermodynamic equilibrium has been attained between loaded and free drug molecules. This equilibrium adsorption process is usually illustrated through the Langmuir isotherm.^[12] Intercalation is another way in which active substances interact with HNT during loading. The molecules enter the interlayer and cause expansion of these layers. Tubular entrapment or vacuum method is another method of interaction and is the one used in this study.^[8, 13] This method can give high loading efficiency when carried out properly and is effective in applications where slow release of functional material is desired over a long period of time such as biocides, drugs, proteins, corrosion inhibitors for metal protection, and surfactants for oil spill remediation^[14-18] Equal amounts of active material and HNT are used together with a suitable solvent. The wetted HNT is placed in vacuum and atmospheric pressure is restored. This is called vacuum pumping and the process is repeated three to four times.^[13]

The interlayer space of HNT has been used as a vehicle to transport substances as diverse as organic small molecules (*e.g.* metoprolol tartrate, salicylic acid, benzotriazole, 2-mercaptobenzothiazole, 2-mercaptobenzimidazole),^[13, 16] polymers (*e.g.* alginate)^[19] and metal nanoparticles, enhancing their biocompatibility and performance as catalysts.^[10] Some examples include the entrapment of gold and ruthenium nanoparticles,^[20, 21] CeO_x and Cu_{3-x}P nanocrystals,^[22, 23] using in-situ growth methods. This allows control of the

uniformity, distribution and size of the nanoparticles within the lumen of the HNT due to confinement effects.

Lauric acid (LA) (dodecanoic acid), is a saturated fatty acid that is found naturally in various vegetable fats, particularly in coconut oil and palm kernel oil. LA possesses strong antibacterial, antiviral, and antifungal activities and it is often used in cosmetic and personal care products.^[24-26] At room temperature, LA is typically in a solid state, forming a white, crystalline substance. In soaps and cosmetics, the solid structure of LA is advantageous. However, its high degree of crystallinity can be detrimental to other useful applications, such as its use as a biocide in water. Molecular confinement in nanometer spaces is one of the methods used to change the (macro) molecular crystallinity.^[27-29] Depending on the confinement space, crystallization can even be completely suppressed, as in the case of intercalation of ethylene glycol and poly(ethylene oxide) into the sub nanometric interlayer space of graphite oxide.^[30]

Present study explores how the intercalation of LA into halloysite nanotubes (i-LA/HNT) can be an efficient method to promote fatty acid transportation and a way to reduce its crystallinity. With this aim, LA intercalated into HNT by using vacuum method and ethanol as a vehicle to deposit the fatty acid inside the nanotube. As a reference sample, a mixture of LA and HNT was prepared without vacuum and with a very short contact time (m-LA/HNT). To monitor the effect of the quality of HNT on the intercalation of LA, two batches of HNT from the same supplier were used. The formation of intercalates was proved by a combination of techniques that include thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), nitrogen physisorption, wide-angle and small-angle X-ray scattering techniques (WAXS/SAXS). Moreover, the pH of i-LA/HNT dispersed in deionized water and

seawater was monitored for a month providing useful information about their stability and release profile.

Experimental section

HNT was supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (CAS 1332-58-7, product number 685445) in two different batches, here referred as HNT-I (batch MKCR7148) and HNT-II (batch MKCQ1344). Lauric acid was sourced from Thermoscientific. Ethanol, 99% purity was sourced from PanReac Applichem. All the products were used without any further treatment except the HNT that was pulverized to loosen the particles.

Synthesis of i-LA/HNT: Intercalation of LA into HNT was performed as followed. A saturated solution of LA was prepared by dissolving 1 g of LA in 6 mL of ethanol. The solution was then stirred for 30 min with a magnetic stirrer before 1 g of HNT was added and stirred again for 30 min. The mixture was first freeze dried before taking to vacuum. Under vacuum conditions, the entrapped air in the HNT lumen is replaced by LA at a reduced pressure of 0.1 mBar for about 1 h. This process of vacuum pumping in and out was repeated three times to ensure that the nanotube is well loaded with the LA. The obtained dispersion was then magnetically stirred for 72 h. The nanocomposite was first rinsed with ethanol to remove excess LA which might block the tubes and/or may be attached to the surface of the tube. It was, thereafter, rinsed with deionized water before drying in a vacuum oven at 60 °C. After that, it was put in the desiccator to keep it moisture free.

Synthesis of m-LA/HNT: A reference sample was synthesized in an attempt to prevent intercalation. To do that, 1 g of HNT was mixed with 0.15 g of LA in 3 mL ethanol during

2 min and immediately filtrated. The mixture was dried in a vacuum oven at 60 °C and stored in a desiccator.

The microstructure of HNT was analyzed using TEM on a FEI Tecnai TM G2 20 Twin microscope at 200 kV. The samples were dispersed in ethanol at a concentration of 1 mg/mL and then 3 μ L were deposited on a 300 mesh carbon grid.

The textural properties of HNT and LA/HNT samples were determined by N₂ adsorption-desorption measurements performed at -196 °C in a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 instrument. The materials were outgassed at 30 °C for 72 h under vacuum. The specific surface area (S_{BET}) was determined from the N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms using the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) equation. The t-plot method was used to evaluate the micropore area (S_{mic}). Finally, pore volume (V_{pore}) and pore size distribution were calculated using the method proposed by Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH method).

WAXS experiments were performed on a Bruker D8 Advanced diffractometer operating at 40 kV and 40 mA. This diffractometer works in parallel beam geometry with CuK α transition photons of wavelength $\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$. The linear detector LYNXEYE used presents an active area of 14.4 mm \times 16 mm. The experiments were performed in reflection mode (θ - 2θ configuration), varying the scattering angle 2θ from 5° to 80° with steps of 0.05° and measure times of 5 s/point. The temperature was controlled in an Anton Paar TTK 450 chamber with 1 °C resolution under vacuum conditions. XRD data of LA was registered after heating to 60 °C and cooling back to 25 °C.

SAXS experiments were performed in a Rigaku 3-pinhole PSAXS-L equipment operating at 45 kV and 0.88 mA. The MicroMax-002+ X-ray Generator system is composed by a microfocus sealed tube source module and an integrated X-ray generator unit which produces CuK α transition photons of wavelength $\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$. The flight path and the

sample chamber in this equipment are under vacuum. The scattered X-rays are detected on a two-dimensional multiwire X-ray detector (Gabriel design, 2D-200X), which is a gas-filled proportional type detector that offers a 200 mm diameter active area with ca. 200 micron resolution. After azimuthal integration, the scattered intensities were obtained as a function of the scattering vector Q , $Q = 4\pi\lambda^{-1}\sin(\theta)$, where θ is half the scattering angle. Reciprocal space calibration was done using silver behenate as standard. Samples were filling in sandwich-type sample holders with mica windows placed in a Linkam Scientific Instruments THMS 600 temperature controller (stability of ± 0.1 °C), in transmission geometry, with a sample to detector distance of 2 m covering a q -range between 0.01 \AA^{-1} and 0.20 \AA^{-1} . Experiments were conducted at 25 °C and 50 °C with measuring times of 5 min. The heating and cooling rates were 20 °C/min and the temperature stabilization time before each measurement was 10 min.

TGA experiments were carried out using TGA Q500 from TA Instrument in a temperature range between 30 – 600 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min under a N_2 flow of 60 mL/min. DSC was carried out using Q2000 DSC from TA Instrument. About 5 mg of a sample were measured in a sealed aluminum pan from -50 to 120 °C at 10 °C/min heating and cooling ramps by using helium flow rate of 25 mL/min. This process was repeated twice.

The pH of aqueous dispersions of HNT, i-LA/HNT and m-LA/HNT was monitored for a month by using HORIBA LAQUAtwin pH-33 apparatus. 1 g of the sample were dispersed in 10 mL of milli-Q water or fresh seawater, collected in San Sebastian port, Spain.

Results and discussion

Synthesis of LA/HNT intercalates

The synthesis of i-LA/HNT was conducted using the solvent and vacuum method, employing two different batches of HNT (I and II) and an excess of LA respect to HNT absorption capacity (1 g of LA per 1g of HNT). Ethanol is a good solvent for LA and it acts as a vehicle to deposit the LA inside the nanotube. It is a mild, green solvent and vaporizes easily. The i-LA/HNT samples prepared under these conditions are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of synthesized LA/HNT samples.

Sample	HNT batch	m _{LA} (g)	m _{HNT} (g)	V _{ethanol} (mL)	m _{LA} / m _{LA/HNT} ^a (wt%)	T _m (°C)	ΔH _{m(LA)} (J/g)	C _{LA} (%)
i-LA/HNT-I	I	1	1	6	12	37.5	75	41
i-LA/HNT-II	II	1	1	6	12	39.1	69	38
m-LA/HNT-I	I	0.15	1	3	14	37.0	92	50
m-LA/HNT-II	II	0.15	1	3	13	37.5	56	30

^aDetermined by TGA.

TGA was used to determine the amount of LA in i-LA/HNT compounds. Figure 1a shows the thermal profiles of i-LA/HNT-I, and LA and HNT-I reference samples. As observed, i-LA/HNT-I exhibits a weight loss between 100 and 180 °C, which corresponds to the decomposition of LA. This process occurs at lower temperature than in the bulk LA sample (temperature at the maximum of the derivative = 155 vs. 206 °C) likely due to confinement effects, as previously observed in poly (ethylene oxide)/graphite oxide intercalates.^[31] HNT is thermally stable in this temperature range. Moreover, i-LA/HNT-

I shows a weight loss at 471 °C (temperature at the maximum of the derivative), at a same temperature as in HNT-I, indicating that the HNT structure has been preserved in the intercalate.

Figure 1. TGA data obtained at a heating rate of 10 °C/min under nitrogen atmosphere. The temperature at the maximum of the derivative and ash weights are indicated. (a) Thermal degradation of lauric acid in the bulk and within the i-LA/HNT-I structure. Pristine HNT-I is shown for comparison. (b) Thermal degradation of lauric acid within the different intercalated LA/HNT structures.

The amount of LA in LA/HNT is given by:

$$W_{LA/HNT} = f_{LA}W_{LA} + f_{HNT}W_{HNT} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where $W_{LA/HNT}$, W_{LA} and W_{HNT} are the weight percent of LA/HNT, LA and HNT residues at 600 °C, respectively, and f_{LA} and f_{HNT} are the fractions of LA and HNT in LA/HNT, respectively. Since $f_{HNT} = 1 - f_{LA}$, we can write:

$$f_{LA} = \frac{W_{LA/HNT} - W_{HNT}}{W_{LA} - W_{HNT}} \quad \text{Eq 2.}$$

By using Eq. 2 the amount of LA in the intercalate was calculated as reported in Table 1. In both preparations, using HNT-I and HNT-II, 12 wt% of LA was obtained. The amounts of LA in LA/HNT composites are in agreement with previous works where the loading capacity reported had been mainly 5 wt% to 10 wt% loading.^[32-34]

As a reference sample, to verify the effect of confinement on LA properties, a mixture of LA and HNT was prepared in an attempt to prevent intercalation by using a very short contact time between LA and HNT, and not using vacuum. With this aim, 0.15 g of LA per gram of HNT was used. The amount of LA taken up by HNT in m-LA/HNT samples was verified by TGA, resulting in a similar thermal profile as in i-LA/HNT samples (Figure 1b). In this case, an uptake of 13-14 wt% LA was obtained indicating that all the LA used in the sample preparation was efficiently taken up by HNT (Table 1).

At 240 °C, a step of ~1.5 wt% weight loss was observed in i-LA/HNT-II and m-LA/HNT-II, which was not observed in their analogous samples obtained from HNT-I, suggesting the existence of some compositional and structure differences between HNT-I and HNT-II. These differences were confirmed by analyzing the TGA profile of unfilled HNTs (Figure 2), where the temperature at the maximum of the derivative exhibited an 8-9 °C difference between the two sample batches, 143 vs 152 °C and 467 vs 475 °C for HNT-II and HNT-I, respectively. The first step can be attributed to 0.4 wt% water loss in the interlayer, lumen and unconfined, while the second step to the dehydroxylation of structural OH groups (~14 wt% mass loss).^[35] Furthermore, the absence of weight loss at 240 °C in the pristine HNTs suggests that the weight loss detected in the LA/HNT-II compounds at this temperature (Figure 1b) may be due to the decomposition of ~1.5 wt% of strongly confined LA.

Figure 2. TGA data obtained at a heating rate of 10 °C/min under nitrogen atmosphere of two HNT batches used in this study. The temperature at the maximum of the derivative are indicated.

Morphology and structure of LA/HNT intercalates

Figure 3 shows the TEM images of HNT-I, i-LA/HNT-I and m-LA/HNT-II. Figures 3a and 3d indicates that the nanotubes are not of the same length (L) and diameter (D), but have hollow tubular structures with irregular edges. The tubes have an external diameter (D) of 40-60 nm and an inner diameter (d) of 15-20 nm, while the wall thickness (h) is about 20 nm. In Figures 3b and 3e, the lumen can be seen to be less transparent as a result of confinement and loading of LA, which is in agreement with previous observations.²² The change in the transparency of the lumen observed in Figures 3c and 3f was unexpected, given the fast method used to mix the LA and HNT during preparation and the absence of vacuum. To confirm whether LA was confined or not in HNT under these conditions, further analysis was performed as described below.

Figure 3. TEM of (a, d) HNT-I (b, e) i-LA/HNT-I and (c, f) m-LA/HNT-I.

N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms were used to characterize the texture of HNTs and LA/HNTs (Figure 4a). The data show that all samples conform to type IV with a type H1 hysteresis loop, which suggests that the materials have cylindrical shape mesoporous.^[36] Pristine HNTs exhibit a BET surface area (S_{BET}) of $60 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and a micropore area (S_{mic})

of 4 m²/g. Upon LA loading, both samples i-LA/HNT-I and m-LA/HNT-I, exhibit a dramatic reduction in S_{BET} by half and the disappearance of microporosity (Table 2). A change in the pore size distribution of samples containing LA, with pore diameters shifted to higher values, is clearly seen in Figure 4b. The reduction in pore volume (V_{pore}) of HNTs can be clearly attributed to the incorporation of LA into the HNT structure, blocking some pores between 10-30 nm, and which is accompanied by an increase in pore diameter (D_{pore}) for both, i-LA/HNT-I and m-LA/HNT-I. The slight differences found between these two samples in the pore size distribution analysis may be related to the sample preparation, which may result in a more homogeneous distribution of LA chains within the HNTs due to the use of vacuum in the i-LA/HNT-I sample.

Figure 4. (a) N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms. (b) Pore size distribution obtained from the adsorption isotherms.

Table 2. Textural data of HNTs and LA/HNTs.

Sample	S_{BET} (m^2/g)	S_{mic} (m^2/g)	V_{pore} (cm^3/g)	D_{pore} (nm)
HNT-I	60	4	0.27	18
i-LA/HNT-I	27	0	0.20	30
m-LA/HNT-I	24	0	0.18	30

WAXS analysis of original HNT exhibits a (001) diffraction peak at $q = 0.837 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ ($2\theta = 11.73^\circ$), corresponding to a multilayer wall spacing of 7.5 \AA (Figure 5b). This can be ascribed to halloysite-7 \AA .^[1, 2] The diffraction patterns in Figures 5c and 5d show that the spacing of i-LA/HNT-I and m-LA/HNT-I remained unchanged, indicating that no intercalation of LA into the interlayer of tube walls occurs. In addition, the most intense (100) diffraction peak of LA crystals at 23.7° was not detected in either LA/HNT sample, nor were the less intense peaks (Figure 5a), probably due to the low amount of LA in the intercalate ($\sim 12\%$) and a decrease in the crystallinity of LA.^[37]

Figure 5. XRD patterns recorded at 25°C (WAXS). *From silicon wafer.

SAXS data recorded in the q -region $0.01 - 0.2 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ revealed changes in the curve shape of HNT-I upon LA intercalation (Figure 6). These results qualitatively indicate an increase in the internal-HNT diameter due to the penetration of LA into the lumen in both sample preparations, confirming microscopy observations in i-LA/HNT-I and m-LA/HNT-I. By heating the samples to $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, above the melting temperature of LA (described below) a further change in the SAXS curves was observed for the HNT containing LA, but not for empty HNT. These results suggest that the expansion of the tube dimensions can be attributed to the filling of empty volumes by LA, which, upon heating, occupies a greater volume compared to LA crystals. Similar X-ray diffraction results were obtained for HNT-II sample series corroborating previous observations (Figures S2 and S3). Additionally, pristine HNT-I and HNT-II exhibited similar X-ray diffraction profiles (Figures S3a and S3b), which indicate similar geometrical and shape structure despite the differences found in previous TGA analysis (Figure 2), which indicates slight differences in their chemical composition.

Figure 6. SAXS patterns recorded at 25 and 50 °C.

Crystallization of LA in LA/HNT intercalates

To further study the effect of confinement on the LA crystallization, DSC was employed (Figure 7). HNT did not exhibit any thermal transition in the temperature range investigated, as expected. The melting temperature of LA in the sample (T_m) was reduced from 45.8 °C in bulk sample to 37.5 °C in i-LA/HNT-I, and the melting enthalpy suffered a reduction from 177 J/g in bulk LA sample to 75 J/g in i-LA/HNT-I. Note that the melting enthalpy of LA in the sample ($\Delta H_{m(LA)}^s$) was calculated by normalizing 9.0 J/g obtained for the whole i-LA/HNT-I sample with respect to LA amount in the intercalate, that is 12% (Table 1). The crystallization temperature (T_c) of LA was also reduced from 41.1 °C (single peak) to 22.4 °C and 14.7°C (double peak) in i-LA/HNT-I. These significant differences in the thermal properties of LA are due to confinement as previously observed in a number of systems.^[29-31, 37] Both, intercalation within the nanotubes and adsorption onto the nanotube walls, are known to produce such thermal effects.

Figure 7. DSC data obtained at a heating and cooling rates of 10 °C/min.

Previous results were confirmed in a second batch of i-LA/HNT-II synthesized from HNT-II (Figure 8). DSC data showed only slight differences in T_m , T_c and $\Delta H_{m(LA)}^s$ between batch I and batch II indicating reproducibility of the results but also a slight dependence on the starting HNT material. As shown below, both HNT batches present different pH values when dispersed in water suggesting different ion contents. DSC data of m-LA/HNT-I exhibited unexpectedly only slight differences in T_m and $\Delta H_{m(LA)}^s$ respect to i-LA/HNT-I (Figure 8). The major difference was found in the crystallization peak by showing only one peak at a $T_c \sim 22^\circ\text{C}$ compared to double peak in i-LA/HNT-I, which might suggest the formation of different crystal domains.^[25, 38] These results were verified with a second set of samples prepared with HNT-II, where the data exhibited good reproducibility respect to m-LA/HNT-I.

Figure 8. DSC data obtained at a heating and cooling rates of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

DSC experiments of LA/HNT compounds on one hand confirm that LA was deposited within the HNT lumen by experimenting a change in its percentage of crystallinity

($C_{LA}(\%)$), calculated from Eq. 3 (Table 1). $\Delta H_{m(LA)}^s$ was calculated by normalizing the obtained melting enthalpy with respect to LA amount in the sample. The melting enthalpy of pure LA ($\Delta H_{m(LA)}^p$) was obtained from the literature (183.2 J/g).^[39] The results show $C_{LA}(\%)$ values below 50 % indicating that the majority of confined LA is in its amorphous state. On the other hand, DSC confirms that the crystallization behavior of LA in i-LA/HNT differs from that in m-LA/HNT, which suggests that LA is confined within a different pore size or environment, as observed in the pore size distribution of Figure 4b.

$$C_{LA}(\%) = \frac{\Delta H_{m(LA)}^s}{\Delta H_{m(LA)}^p} \cdot 100\% \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Final remarks on LA intercalation

Both preparations, i-LA/HNT and m-LA/HNT, have similar amounts of incorporated LA and similar physical properties regardless of the synthesis procedure, suggesting that LA can be readily confined within the HNT without the need for vacuum. These were unintended and unexpected results. Vacuum assists solvent flow through the capillary of the HNT lumen. However, there are many other parameters that may affect LA confinement and adsorption to the HNT walls that deserve future investigation. Both ethanol and LA must diffuse toward the HNT wall (internal and external) and competitively come into contact with different sites where they adsorb. For LA there is a third process, the adsorption occurs by changing the chain conformation, which minimizes the free energy. Then there is an exchange between free and adsorbed molecules until an equilibrium is reached. The results obtained for m-LA/HNT suggest that the kinetics of all these processes are very fast in ethanol, allowing the retention of all the LA from the feed in a few minutes during sample preparation.

pH of LA/HNT in water

LA is a weak acid with a pKa near 5.^[26, 40] Its solubility in water at room temperature is very low. If it is released from the intercalate, dissolved in water, the pH of the test media should decrease. Following this hypothesis we monitored the pH of water dispersions of i-LA/HNT intercalates and compared the results with those of HNT and m-LA/HNT samples obtained from HNT-I and HNT-II. Release studies were performed in deionized water and seawater (Figures 9a-d).

Figure 9. pH of HNT, i-LA/HNT and m-LA/HNT in deionized water (a) and (b), and seawater (c) and (d).

Figures 9a and 9b show that LA/HNT in deionized water have a more acidic pH compared to their pristine HNTs, indicating the release of LA. Both, i-LA/HNT and m-LA/HNT samples showed similar pH values, but with a slightly different profile at shorter times, likely due to a different location of LA in the nanotubes. These results were similar for the two intercalated samples, I and II, although in a different pH range. These differences can be attributed to the starting HNT, which showed very different initial pH values, 7.1 (HNT-I) vs 5.2 (HNT-II). Moreover, HNT-I exhibited an apparent acidification with time, whereas HNT-II exhibited the opposite tendency. The pH changes in pristine HNTs are the result of the acid-base equilibria that occur on the inner and outer surfaces of HNTs due to the deprotonation and protonation of AlOH and SiOH groups.^[41] Our results indicate that even though the samples are from the same supplier, the chemical compositions of the samples differ. This underscores the need for thorough characterization of HNT prior to use. In addition, the greater pH variation over time for HNT (e.g. Figure 9b) compared to LA/HNT intercalates may be the result of HNT surface deprotonation. This process is likely to be more limited when an LA layer is adsorbed on the surface.

Release studies of i-LA/HNT and m-LA/HNT in seawater showed similar release profiles as in deionized water, based on the observation of a decrease in the pH of the test media. In this case, an acidification with time was observed in both HNT-I and HNT-II although with a different tendency, steeper in HNT-I (Figure 9c). In seawater, which is a high ionic strength medium, the presence of salts affects the acid-base equilibria that occur in HNTs, as previously reported.^[41] This, together with the different chemical compositions of HNT-I and HNT-II, would explain the different pH variations observed for HNTs in distilled water and seawater.

Conclusions

We have successfully synthesized lauric acid (LA) / halloysite nanotube (HNT) intercalates using ethanol as a vehicle for LA entrapment. A series of two samples were synthesized using vacuum and slow deposition, while another two samples were synthesized using very short contact time and no vacuum. The unexpected intercalation of LA in the latter suggests a very fast intercalation and adsorption kinetics, which deserves to be studied in further investigations. In all cases 12-14 wt% of LA acid was deposited, regardless of the synthesis method used. The evidence of confinement of LA in HNT was provided by several methods. DSC revealed a decrease in LA crystallinity by more than 50% upon confinement. Additionally, TEM data showed a loss of transparency in the lumen of the HNTs, while SAXS data indicated an increase in the internal diameter of the HNTs, suggesting penetration of LA into the lumen in both sample preparations. Nitrogen physisorption analysis supported these results by showing a decrease in BET area and pore volume in LA/HNT samples compared to pristine HNT. Release studies of LA from the intercalates in deionized and seawater showed acidification of aqueous media with pH tending towards 5 or lower, which mainly depended on the initial HNT and the initial pH of water. From these findings, it can be concluded that the quality of the starting HNT is important for data reproducibility, and vacuum may not be necessary to achieve intercalation of functional materials in HNT. This finding holds promise for systems exploring various applications of HNT nanocomposites and for slow-release systems.

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